

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1

**Protocol for Pig Feces collection
and
Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)**

[Compartment 1]

**Version 1
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Protocol for Pig Feces collection and Laboratory Operating Procedure (LOP)

A. Description

Compilation the sampling of pig feces and points, and further laboratory analysis, ensuring harmonization of testing procedures, which will enhance comparability of the results obtained from different regions of Europe. This protocol will allow answering to different questions from the FED-AMR project.

B. Equipment and material

- Sterile propylene flasks, 50ml
- Sterile plastic bags
- Sterile disposable wooden spatula
- Scale
- Sterile cryotubes

C. Procedure

1. Sampling, transportation and conservation

- Consent for fecal sample collection is given by the pig farmer/HOAL. All procedures involving healthy pig animals are performed in accordance with the European regulations regarding the protection of animals used for experimental and other scientific purposes.
- The age of pigs, if they are pregnant sows, as well as antibiotic consumption (amount and dates), and location of the samples taken from cohorts at each time points, will be recorded, and provided in a "Record sheet".
- Samples are collected at the same time each day:
 - o when possible (Portugal), individually, directly from the rectum of each pig (Fig 1) to minimize contamination; aseptically collect the targeted pig gut section (rectum/cloaca);
 - o if at all impossible directly from the rectum (Great Britain, Czech Republic and Estonia), freshly voided feces from healthy pig might be collected from the soil, but it must be from the top of a recent deposit of each pig (Fig 1), and avoiding deposit areas in contact with the ground;
- Fresh fecal samples are collected at **four time points** (See Sample references for pig feces samples, and Table: Sampling timeline by country) in one cohort of pigs on a barn/farm belonging to each of three HOALs (in different countries: Portugal, Estonia and Czech Republic), and in a barn/farm in Great Britain.

- Collected samples are introduced into a plastic bag or a screw cap container that is airtight, watertight, and suitably robust (e.g. 50 ml falcon).
- Subsequently, double-packaging within sealed plastic bags will help prevent cross-contamination of samples and associated packaging materials. [Note: Feces contained only in rectal exam gloves, plastic bags, or rubber-stoppered tubes are unsuitable as they are very frequently comprised by bacterial growth with gas production that can rupture plastic bags, displace stoppers, and allow leakage of the specimen].
- All containers must be clearly and completely labelled (see the coding system at the FED-AMR homepage, and in Table: Sampling timeline by country).
- Conserve immediately samples at **0°C to 5°C** (DO NOT FREEZE FECAL SAMPLES) during transportation to the laboratory and until processed.
- Process the samples within 18 hours.

Note: tubes and samples should be labelled according to the FED-AMR coding system, to be easily identify the sample. See information about this coding system at FED-AMR homepage (under WP1).

2. Sampling processing

2.1. *Individual samples*

We have 30 individual tubes from the sampling with 15 g of feces each or more. From these, distribute samples as displayed in Figure 1 (Note: it should be accounted for weighing errors and sample loss while transferring between tubes):

- 2.75 g of each sample, in 30 tubes (because qPCR1 it is performed with individual samples: 2.5 g for eDNA and 0.25 g for total DNA);
- 1 g of each sample in 30 cryotubes (to store at -80°C as a backup, being sure that it should only be used as last resort, because eDNA will be considerably changed in this frozen sample, and bacteriology results will be also changed; glycerol can be used);
- 1 g of each sample will be used in pools samples for bacteriology (see 2.2.. *pooling* chapter);
- The remaining ± 10 g of each sample will be used to create the composite sample (see 3. *Composite sample* chapter).

2.2. *Pooling*

Pools should be made from fresh faecal samples, during the initial processing of the procedure (do not freeze faecal samples due to the eDNA). Perform **6 pools** for bacteriology as displayed in Figure 1:

- Distribute the 30 individual samples in 6 pools of 5 samples of 1 g each; [**Use always an equal amount** of each of the fresh samples for these 6 pools];
- Mix the samples very well by stirring thoroughly with a sterile disposable wooden spatula, or other sterile device, for 1-2 minutes. From each of these pools:

- weight 0.5 g for WP2 (follow separate protocol for cultivation bacteria in nutrient and minimal media; identification of agreed bacterial genera; MICs; WGS from selected bacteria);
- weight 1 g for WP3 (identification of *Clostridium difficile*; MICs; WGS from selected bacteria).

Fig 1. Pigs feces sampling at 4 time points (composite sample and subsamples), to be performed by Portugal, Czech Republic, Estonia, and Great Britain.

2.3. Composite sample

Perform a **composite sample** by using always an equal amount of each of the fresh samples for this pool, as follows:

- From the remaining ± 10 g of fresh feces weigh rigorously 10 g of each individual sample and pool into a sterile larger container to obtain a composite sample per barn/farm (1 pool). [**Use always** an equal amount of each of the fresh samples for these 6 pools];
- Mix the samples very well by stirring thoroughly with a sterile disposable wooden spatula, or other sterile device, for 1-2 minutes. From this composite sample (1 pool):
 - weight 2.75 g (in triplicate) to be used in 3 DNA extractions for metagenomics (WP2);
 - weight 2.75 g for qPCR2 (WP2);
 - weight 40 g to be used in quantification of antimicrobials (WP4.4);
 - weight 230 g to be used in quantification of trace elements (WP4.7);
 - freeze at -80°C the remaining 19 g of the composite sample.

3. For the representativeness of sample

It is very important:

- to **use always** an equal amount of each of the fresh samples for each types of pools;
- to be sure that a scale with at least two decimal-points are used, to ensure correct weighing of the required amounts;
- to **mix very well** the pooled sample, before using it for DNA extraction (WP2), or bacteriology (WP2, WP3), or quantification (WP4).

4. Conservation in the laboratory and transport to other European regions

- for Bacteriology procedures (WP2, WP3): transport and conservation at 0°C to 5°C until bacteriology be processed, which must be with fresh pooled samples [cultivable bacteria and MICs to be performed in each country];
- for Quantification in WP4.4: feces pool is transported freezed, in 200ml dark PP or PET bottles;
- for Quantification in WP4.7: feces pool is transported freezed, in PET bottles;
- for Genomics (WP2): conservation at 0°C to 5°C until extraction of DNA; DNA extraction must be processed within the next 18h due to eDNA [using harmonized protocol; to be performed in each country].; [if any country cannot performed it in the respective lab, DNA should be shipped at -80°C to the receptor lab, which MTA will be prepared by WP1].

5. Sample references for pig feces samples

Estonia:

Sample Reference	Description	Schedule Month
EE20-P1	Estonia, pig barn, summer	Ago-20
EE20-P2	Estonia, pig barn, autumn	Oct-20
EE20-P3	Estonia, pig barn, winter	Fev-21
EE20-P4	Estonia, pig barn, spring	Abr-21

Czech Republic:

Sample Reference	Description	Schedule Month
CZ20-P1	Czech Republic, pig barn, spring	May 20
CZ20-P2	Czech Republic, pig barn, summer	Ago-20
CZ20-P3	Czech Republic, pig barn, autumn	Oct 20
CZ20-P4	Czech Republic, pig barn, winter	Dec 20

Great Britain:

Sample Reference	Description	Schedule Month
GB20-P1	Great Britain, pig barn, summer	Jul 2020
GB20-P2	Great Britain, pig barn, autumn	Oct 2020
GB21-P3	Great Britain, pig barn, winter	Jan 2021
GB21-P4	Great Britain, pig barn, spring	Apr 2021

Portugal:

Sample Reference	Description	Schedule Month
PT20-P1	Portugal, pig barn, summer	Jul-20
PT20-P2	Portugal, pig barn, autumn	Out-20
PT21-P3	Portugal, pig barn, winter	Jan-21
PT21-P4	Portugal, pig barn, spring	Abr-21

D. References:

- EFFORT protocols (e.g. D2.1., D.1.5.)
- General Collection and Handling of Fecal Samples. University of Prince Edward Island (UPEI).
- OIE Terrestrial Manual 2018, Sampling methods (Chapter I.1.1, page 1-11)
- OIE Terrestrial Manual 2018, Collection, submission and storage of diagnostic specimens (Chapter 1.1.2., page 11-22)
- Schmidt GV, Mellerup A, Christiansen LE, Ståhl M, Olsen JE, Angen Ø. 2015. Sampling and Pooling Methods for Capturing Herd Level Antibiotic Resistance in Swine Feces using qPCR and CFU Approaches. PLoS ONE 10(6): e0131672. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0131672.
- Metzler-Zebeli BU, Lawlor PG, Magowan E, Zebeli Q. 2016. Animals (Basel), 6(3). pii: E18. doi: 10.3390/ani6030018.